

Exploring the relationship between telework and housing space: Empirical evidence for Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the relationship between telework and the housing space in Switzerland, drawing on sufficiency-oriented sustainability debates. While teleworking is often discussed as a measure to reduce commuting-related emissions, its implications for housing space have received little empirical attention. Using a unique survey of 948 tenant households living in 3- to 5.5-room dwellings in urban agglomerations in German-speaking Switzerland, we analyse the likelihood of teleworking and its association with housing space per person. A probit model identifies the socio-demographic, spatial and housing-related factors that increase the probability of teleworking, while an OLS model examines whether telework is linked to higher housing space per person. The results show that teleworkers use on average six square metres more housing space per person. This can partly be related to teleworking and partly to the socio-economic characteristics of households that are more likely to telework. The findings suggest that telework may contribute to rising housing space and thus poses challenges for sustainable housing. The study offers the first empirical evidence on this relationship for Switzerland and highlights the need to address spatial spillover effects in future housing and sustainability policies.

1. Introduction

As teleworking becomes more widespread, its contribution to sustainability and sufficiency becomes increasingly important. Telework is defined as paid work conducted outside the traditional boundaries of the employer workplace such as the office or the production site [1,2]. In this paper, we refer to telework as working from home. The Federal Statistical Office in Switzerland [3] estimates that approximately 37% of the Swiss labour force engages in regular teleworking.

Teleworking has mainly been discussed as a way to reduce the environmental impact of commuting [2], as it reduces commuting frequency (e.g. [1,4,5]). However, teleworking may also generate rebound effects, such as longer commuting distances resulting from increased residential flexibility or additional leisure mobility (e.g. for Switzerland [6]). In addition, spillover effects may occur, including the duplication of information and communication technology (ICT) devices or

increased housing space due to the need for separate home office space [7]. So far, especially the implication of teleworking for housing space have received comparatively less attention.

A sufficiency-oriented perspective complements conventional sustainability approaches by emphasising limits to consumption and aiming to reduce resource use while maintaining social standards [8,9]. This is particularly relevant in housing because housing space in Switzerland has increased disproportionately to population growth [10]. Average housing space per person rose from 34 m² in 1980 to over 46.6 m² in 2024 [11,12]. This development is driven by factors such as larger dwellings, rising prosperity, and demographic changes, including smaller households and an ageing population [10,13]. As teleworking shifts paid work into the home, it may further intensify demand for housing space, potentially reinforcing this trend, for example through the need for dedicated workspace or larger dwellings [14,15]. Consequently, potential environmental savings from reduced commuting may

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be partially counterbalanced by expanded housing space [16,17].

This study contributes theoretically by explaining how telework may reshape housing space. Rather than treating housing space as a fixed background condition, it conceptualizes housing space as an outcome of shifting work practices into the home [18,19]. The study argues that telework can increase demand for work-related housing space because households need to accommodate productivity requirements, everyday routines, and boundaries between paid work and private life within the home. In doing so, it links telework research with housing research and sufficiency-oriented sustainability debates. This study examines the link between telework and housing space and represents one of the first empirical analysis of this relationship in Switzerland. Since housing space depends on household-specific factors, we first analyse the characteristics of teleworkers in our sample. In a second step, we examine the relationship between teleworking and housing space. Specifically, we ask whether teleworking is associated with higher levels of housing space. Using survey data from 948 households in Switzerland, analyses provide empirical evidence that both sociodemographic and housing-related factors influence the likelihood of teleworking. The results further indicate that teleworking affects per person housing space through housing-specific and objective factors.

Our paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the existing literature. Section 3 presents the background of study, the data and methodology. The key results are described in Section 4 and Section 5 provides a discussion of the overall findings and concludes with implications for further research.

2. Teleworking and the impacts on housing space

We start by discussing the aspects that influence the likelihood of teleworking and then explain the correlations between telework, housing preferences and housing space.

2.1. Who are the teleworkers?

The widespread adoption of ICT has facilitated teleworking by virtualising tasks and making paid work more flexible in terms of space and time [1,20,21]. The prevalence of teleworking has increased significantly in recent years, particularly in the wake of the covid-19 pandemic. Nowadays, teleworkers are not a homogeneous group [22], but certain groups of people are shown to practice telework more often than others [23,24]. Individual, household, and job-related characteristics influence the likelihood of engaging in telework. Related to education, Peters et al. [25] found that individuals with higher education levels, especially a university degree, and those with advanced IT skills are more likely to telework. Similarly, López-Igual and Rodríguez-Modroño [26] confirmed that both education and employment status strongly influence the likelihood of teleworking, although opportunities have increasingly extended to lower-status or precarious jobs.

Several studies report gender differences, with women being generally less likely to telework than men [27,26]. Similarly, Singh et al. [28] show that women are less likely to have access to teleworking opportunities, but are more likely to make use of them when available. Further, López-Igual and Rodríguez-Modroño [26] show that for women with children under the age of 15, the probability of teleworking increase after the birth of a second child. Moreover, gender-specific preferences and sectoral opportunities contribute to these differences, as the availability and attractiveness of telework vary across industries and occupations [27,29]. Analysing gender differences in both the ability and motivations for telework is essential, as men and women perceive and experience teleworking differently [30]. These differences are reflected, for example, in the reasons for engaging in telework and how individuals use the time saved from commuting [31].

In addition, consumption-related factors refer to behaviours and housing conditions associated with everyday resource consumption,

including commuting patterns [32,33] and housing characteristics such as room layout and housing space [34,35]. People with longer or frequent commutes make greater use of telework [32,33]. At the same time, suitable housing conditions, such as sufficient space or a separate workroom promote the practical feasibility of telework [34,35]. Moreover, teleworking practices differ according to workplace and residential geography. Vilhelmson and Thulin [21] found for Sweden that employees living in larger urban areas were more likely to telework than those living in rural regions. In urban centers, which are often characterized by knowledge-intensive industries, the proportion of teleworkers is significantly higher than in rural areas [36,37].

As a key motivation for teleworking, it is associated with increased autonomy, efficiency, and work performance [38]. Teleworking provides spatial flexibility and autonomy, enabling employees to better manage their time schedules and improve paid work-life balance [39]. It also allows individuals to adjust working hours to personal needs, strengthening control over the boundaries between paid work and private life [40]. However, teleworking may simultaneously constrain well-being due to the increased interpenetration of life domains and blurring the distinction between work and family life [41] and may also reinforce inequalities between household members in unpaid household and care work [42,43].

2.2. Telework and housing space

Telework is reshaping the relationship with housing, as homes increasingly serve as workplaces. At the same time, it may shift housing preferences and residential location decisions, as proximity to the workplace becomes less important. The home is a lived space for people, places and things, both physical and digital [44]. With the shift of paid work into the home and their domestic practices, the home has also become a physical base for paid work [18]. Therefore, teleworking has profoundly changed the meaning and content of homes [19,45]. Hence, telework can also reconfigure domestic practices, temporal routines and expectations towards housing. Early research already showed that home-based telework reshapes the synchronization of paid work and family life and triggers new negotiations over boundaries between paid work and private and availability within the home [46].

Telework changes the allocation of time and the organization of everyday practices, and these shifts may trigger rebound and spillover effects ([6,7]), for example through longer commuting distances or increased housing space use. When regular presence at the employer's workplace becomes less necessary and the number of days at the regular workplace is reduced, residential choice may expand geographically because workplace proximity loses some of its relevance [47] and longer commuting distances can be accepted [48,49]. It can also be associated with a greater willingness to live farther from urban centres when housing conditions are more favourable [50].

Teleworking increases the importance of the home as a multifunctional space and making certain aspects of home environment more relevant [51]. Teleworking affects the home by repurposing spaces, increasing the need for separation and privacy, introducing new scheduling requirements to balance paid work, caregiving, and leisure, and creating competition for domestic resources such as home offices and digital infrastructure [52]. Kawabuko and Arata [53] distinguish between desk, workspace and home environments, whereas teleworking is effective for some tasks and individuals, but depends heavily on the home environment and personality. Sufficient space, a quiet area, and appropriate equipment become more important than they are in a purely office-based work environment and a lack of physical separation between paid work and private life can be problematic because it hinders productivity and disrupts routines [54]. Further, Asadieh and Neisch [55] show that housing environments characteristics such as the availability of a separate office room indirectly enhance productivity, which subsequently influences telework satisfaction and increases the likelihood of continued teleworking. Magnier-Watanabe et al. [56] identify

the home workspace as a key determinant of telework satisfaction, arguing that teleworking increases demands on housing space environment and thus favours home that provide physical separation. Such separate home office arrangements can improve concentration and help preserve boundaries between paid work and private life [57]. Further these changes in domestic practices can translate into changing housing preferences. Teleworking experience has been found to increase the value attached to housing attributes such as high-quality office space at home [50]. Many teleworkers adapt their homes to suit teleworking, for example by purchasing additional monitors [45].

The suitability of the housing environment for teleworking may also differ, particularly with regard to the availability of dedicated workspace [58]. Shirmohammadi et al. [52] note that the ability to adapt housing spaces for telework depends on the material and financial resources of the household. Teleworkers may seek larger homes in order to create a separate home office room [59,60]. Nilles [35] demonstrates that teleworkers tend to occupy larger homes than non-teleworkers. Regardless of causality the fact that teleworking requires more space is one of the factors influencing the continuous tendency that home are getting larger, as can be seen in Canadian cities by Moos and Skaburskis [14], p. 326. Larger homes are associated with a higher environmental impact compared to smaller or more compact housing types [61]. In the long term, teleworking and the growing demand for a separate home office room could have significant implications for housing. The findings suggest that teleworking increases the demand for additional or specialized housing space not only by shifting the location of paid work, but also because the home must increasingly meet work-related requirements regarding productivity, privacy, and boundary management.

In general, dwelling size is influenced by a variety of factors, for example household characteristics such as income, age or number of people [8,62], housing preferences and lifestyle (e.g. teleworking), as well as market conditions and economic influences such as availability of housing [63]. In general, housing space preferences are constrained by budgets and shaped by family life cycle stages [64].

2.3. Conclusion

Several assumptions can be formulated to examine the relationship between teleworking and various individual, household-related, and housing-specific factors. Individuals with higher education levels and those employed in high-skilled or knowledge-intensive occupations are more likely to engage in telework, as their task can often be performed independently of a specific workplace. Sociodemographic characteristics such as gender and age may also shape telework participation, given persistent structural differences in labour market participation and occupational status. Furthermore, housing-specific factors including the number of rooms in a dwelling and geographical location can influence the feasibility of teleworking. Similarly, the availability of a dedicated workspace or separate home office room at home tend to facilitate the practical implementation of telework. Consequently, the adoption of teleworking may itself affect housing demand, as teleworking households may require additional space to establish a dedicated workspace.

From a housing perspective, telework may lead to an expansion of work-related space at home. This is particularly relevant when teleworkers combine several workplaces, since work is no longer concentrated in one single location. Instead, part of the housing space may be functionally transformed into workspace, or additional space may be required to establish a dedicated telework setting. It is therefore hypothesized that teleworking is associated with a larger amount of housing space.

This conceptual framework enables a differentiated analysis of the social, occupational, and spatial characteristics and implications of teleworking. However, the reciprocal relationship between these factors and teleworking points to a potential endogeneity issue: while individual, household, and housing-specific characteristics influence the

likelihood of teleworking, teleworking itself may shape housing demand and housing space. This bidirectional relationship implies that explanatory factors and outcomes may interact simultaneously. Therefore, the analysis identifies associations rather than causal effects and the results should be interpreted as descriptive correlations that illustrate the structural and spatial contexts in which teleworking occurs.

3. Data and empirical models

3.1. Data

The data used in our study was originally collected by a survey as part of a research project on the planification of rental dwellings, focusing on potential substitution relationships between housing space and housing quality. The survey collected data on housing satisfaction, patterns of housing use, and general housing preferences as well as sociodemographic characteristics. The target group for the survey was defined in line with the project objectives and included tenant households in the German-speaking part of Switzerland living in 3- to 5.5-room dwellings, where the oldest household member is not older than 65 years, and residing in agglomeration municipalities with an urban character according to the Swiss Federal Statistical Office (FSO) definition. The online survey was conducted in November 2022 with the support of a market research institute. Households defined according to the target group criteria were invited via email to participate in the survey, with a request that the questionnaire be completed by a person who had (co-)signed the rental contract for the dwelling. Participation in the survey was entirely voluntary. All participants provided written informed consent for their anonymized data to be used for scientific research purposes.

The final sample comprises a total of 972 households, with 401 households living in 3- or 3.5-room dwellings, 401 households in 4- or 4.5-room dwellings, and 179 households in 5- or 5.5-room dwellings and is representative with respect to the distribution of 3 to 5.5-room dwellings in Switzerland. In 2024, 3- to 5-room dwellings dominated the Swiss housing market, comprising about 69% of the total stock (27.1% 3-room, 27.3% 4-room, 14.8% 5-room; [12]). This distribution allows the analysis to encompass the majority of Swiss dwellings, which can be regarded as broadly comparable in character.

3.2. Empirical models

The empirical analysis follows a two-step approach. First, we estimate a probit model to examine the likelihood of teleworking, and second, we use an OLS model to analyse the relationship between teleworking and housing space. Both models include a comparable set of control variables such as sociodemographic, housing-specific, and location-specific characteristics, while Model 2 additionally incorporates the telework indicator as the main explanatory variable. This sequential design allows us to distinguish between the determinants and the spatial outcomes of teleworking.

3.2.1. Model 1: Likelihood of teleworking

To analyse the determinants of teleworking, we estimate a probit model, as the dependent variable is binary and indicates whether the respondent (co-)signing the rental contract teleworks at least part of the time (1 = teleworks, 0 = does not telework). The model takes the following functional form, as given by (1):

$$P(y_i = 1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \mathbf{X}_i^{SD} + \beta_2 \mathbf{X}_i^{HW} + \beta_3 \mathbf{X}_i^{LOC}) \quad (1)$$

where $\Phi(\cdot)$ denotes the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution. y_i is a binary variable indicating telework, and y_i^* represents the unobserved latent propensity to telework. The latent variable can be written as:

$$y_i^* = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \mathbf{X}_i^{SD} + \beta_2 \mathbf{X}_i^{HW} + \beta_3 \mathbf{X}_i^{LOC} + \varepsilon_i, \tag{2}$$

with $\varepsilon_i \sim N(0, 1)$.

\mathbf{X}_i^{SD} denotes sociodemographic characteristics (gender, age, household type, number of children under 14 years, and professional status);

\mathbf{X}_i^{HW} represents housing-specific characteristics (use of rooms outside of dwelling and availability of free rooms); and

\mathbf{X}_i^{LOC} includes location-specific factors (degree of urbanisation and use of public transport).

The coefficients β are estimated by maximum likelihood. The marginal effects derived from the estimated coefficients indicate the change in the probability of teleworking associated with a one-unit change in each explanatory variable, holding other factors constant.

3.2.2. Model 2: Housing space

In the second step, we analyse the relationship between teleworking and housing space. The dependent variable measures the amount of housing space per person (in square metres weighted per household member). The main explanatory variable is a binary indicator for telework, corresponding to the dependent variable in Model 1 (1 = teleworks; 0 = does not telework).

To control for differences in household composition, housing conditions, and spatial context, we include several additional variables. These comprise a dummy indicating whether leisure activities take place within the dwelling, the rent per square metre, and individual and household characteristics such as gender, age, household type, number of children under 14 years, and professional status. In addition, an urban indicator is included to account for locational differences.

In contrast to Model 1, only a subset of housing-specific characteristics is included here. Variables such as the number of rooms, the number of free rooms, and the average room size are excluded because they are conceptually and mechanically related to the dependent variable (housing space per person). Including these variables would risk controlling for factors that are part of the outcome itself or that mediate the effect of teleworking on housing space. The model can be expressed by Eq. (3) and is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Housing space per person}_i &= \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Telework}_i \\ &+ \alpha_2 \text{LeisureActivitiesDwelling}_i \\ &+ \alpha_3 \text{RentPerSm}_i + \alpha_4 \mathbf{X}_i^{SD} + \alpha_5 \mathbf{X}_i^{LOC} + u_i, \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where u_i is an error term assumed to satisfy the classical OLS assumptions $E(u_i | \mathbf{X}_i) = 0$ and $\text{Var}(u_i) = \sigma^2$.

We estimate the model using ordinary least squares (OLS) regression with robust standard errors. To strengthen the robustness of the empirical analysis, several model selection procedures and specification checks were conducted during the development of the final model. The additional results confirm the general pattern reported in the main model, while also pointing to some heterogeneity across groups. To rule out multicollinearity among the independent variables, we calculate variance inflation factors (VIF) following Belsley, Kuh, and Welsch [65] and ensure that all values remain below the critical threshold of 10. Furthermore, the error terms were subjected to a homoscedasticity test to verify that the assumption of constant variance is not violated. The coefficient α_1 captures the average difference in housing space between teleworking and non-teleworking households, holding other factors constant.

3.2.3. Causal structure and endogeneity

The relationship between teleworking and housing space is potentially endogenous due to both simultaneity and selection effects [66]. It points to a bidirectional relationship between teleworking and housing space, which has also been discussed in the literature on telework and residential choices (e.g. [14]). In addition, selection effects may arise

because households with higher income, specific occupational characteristics, or stronger preferences for housing space are both more likely to telework and to occupy larger dwellings. As a result, the observed association may partly reflect underlying socio-economic differences rather than a direct effect of teleworking.

While the two-step modelling strategy conceptually separates the determinants of teleworking from its association with housing space and thus helps to structure the analysis and control for observable differences between households, it does not fully resolve the underlying endogeneity. In both models, a broad set of socio-demographic, occupational, and housing-related variables is included to account for observable heterogeneity that may jointly influence teleworking and housing space. Additional specification checks and alternative model formulations were explored and yield qualitatively similar results, suggesting that the observed relationship is not driven by specific modelling choices.

At the same time, the cross-sectional nature of the data and the absence of suitable instrumental variables or longitudinal information limit the extent to which causal relationships can be identified. In particular, the available data do not allow us to disentangle the direction of causality between teleworking and housing space. The findings should therefore be interpreted as conditional associations that reflect structural relationships between both dimensions rather than as causal effects. Taken together, the results indicate a robust association between teleworking and housing space. Table 1 includes the description of the modelling data. The following section describes the data.

3.3. Variables

3.3.1. Model 1

The dependent variable of the first model *Telework_i* is a binary variable that specifies whether at least one person in the household *i* teleworks. This dummy variable takes the value 1 if this is the case and 0 if no member of the household teleworks.

Our independent variables include sociodemographic characteristics of households, housing-related and location-specific characteristics.

Gender was coded as a dummy variable indicating female respondents (reference: male). Age was categorized into three groups: 35–54 years, 55–65 years, and the reference category 18–34 years. Household type distinguishes between single households, couple households with and without children, single-parent families, and others. The number of children under 14 years was included as a continuous variable. Professional status was classified into three categories: low (unskilled; reference group), middle (skilled workers), and high (managerial or professional occupations). The classification is based on the respondent's occupation or job title.

A central focus is on the characteristics of the housing. The variable 'room outside of home' captures whether respondents have access to a separate home office room beyond their main housing area, which can facilitate regular teleworking by providing an appropriate work environment. The 'free rooms indicator' reflects the availability of additional, unused rooms at home. To assess the utilisation of the housing space, a free room indicator is used, which is calculated from the number of rooms minus the number of household members minus one. This assumption is based on an indicator of sufficient housing space occupancy [8]. For example, a three-room dwelling should be occupied by at least two people. In the context of teleworking, a high number of free rooms indicates that a separate home office room is available for teleworking.

Finally, location-specific factors include a dummy variable indicating the use of public transport and a variable capturing the degree of urbanisation. A dummy variable for 'use of public transport' indicates whether public transport is used for commuting. The degree of urbanisation captures the location of the dwellings, differentiated according to urban (as reference), mixed or rural areas in accordance with the municipality typology of the Federal Statistical Office.

Table 1
Description of variables and descriptive statistics.

Variable name	Definition	Value	Mean / %	Telework	Non-Telework
Dependent variables					
Telework	Dummy, equal to 1 if a person teleworks in the household, 0 else	1 yes 0 no	0.63		
Housing space per person	Weighted housing space perm ² person: Housing space of dwelling in m ² divided by the weighted number of persons by household with the following weights: 1 person = 1; 2 = 1.57, 3 = 1.83, 4 = 2.22, 5 = 2.43, 6 +=2.61		64.8	65.8	63.0
Independent variables					
<i>Sociodemographic characteristics</i>					
Gender	Gender of respondent	1 male 2 female	0.43 0.57	0.46 0.53	0.37 0.63
Age category	Age of the respondent calculated as categories	Years 18–34 years 35–54 years 55–65 years	40.0 0.37 0.49 0.14	39.0 0.39 0.50 0.11	41.8 0.33 0.47 0.20
Household type	Type of household	Single Couple w/o children Couple household without children Couple household with children (ren) Single-parent family Shared household (incl. multi-generational households, etc.)	0.20 0.32 0.34 0.08 0.05	0.16 0.35 0.36 0.07 0.06	0.26 0.27 0.32 0.11 0.04
Household size	Number of persons living in the household	Numbers	2.4	2.5	2.3
	Number of children under 14 years of age	Numbers	0.50	0.53	0.45
Professional status	Professional status, calculated based on job title.	Low Middle High Unskilled employees (low), skilled employees (middle), senior management or academic professions (high)	0.20 0.68 0.12	0.16 0.68 0.16	0.27 0.69 0.04
<i>Housing characteristics and preferences</i>					
Room outside of dwelling	Dummy, equal to 1 if a person in the household also uses other rooms outside the dwelling, 0 else	1 yes 0 no		0.17	0.10
Dwelling use for leisure activities	Dummy, equal to 1 if a person in the household also uses the home for hobbies, 0 else	1 yes 0 no	0.58	0.61	0.53
Rent per square meter	Rent per square meter (m ²) per month for dwelling, in Swiss Francs	Number	18.9	19.3	18.3
Free room indicator	Free room indicator represents an under occupancy leading to free rooms for other purposes, calculated as the number of rooms minus the number of people –1 (in vein of [8])	Numbers	0.35	0.34	0.38
<i>Location-specific characteristic</i>					
Public transport use	Dummy, equal to 1 if a person mainly uses public transport to get to paid work and run their daily errands, 0 else	1 yes 0 no	0.47	0.52	0.38
Degree of urbanization	The variable <i>degree of urbanization</i> distinguishes between urban, mixed, and rural municipalities, according to the municipality typology of the Federal Statistical Office FSO	Urban Mixed Rural	0.69 0.25 0.05	0.70 0.26 0.04	0.68 0.24 0.08

The table reports descriptive statistics of our regression variables. The number of observations is 948.

3.3.2. Model 2

The dependent variable of the second model, *Housing Space Per Person_i*, measures the weighted housing space per person in household *i*. It is calculated based on the total housing space of the dwelling and the number of persons permanently residing in the household. To account for household size effects, the variable is adjusted using an equivalence weighting following Glatzer [67], p. 47. This approach assumes that the optimal housing space per person does not increase proportionally with the number of household members [13]. As household size grows, the optimal per person housing space rises at a degressive rate, reflecting economies of scale in housing space. The weighted value is obtained by dividing the total housing space by the household's equivalence weight.

As independent variables, we include in addition to Model 1 several key independent variables capturing work and housing characteristics. The dummy variable 'telework' indicates whether respondents regularly telework. This variable represents the central explanatory factor and allows for identifying differences between teleworkers and non-teleworkers in terms of housing space per person. The dummy variable 'dwelling use for leisure activities' captures whether respondents report using the dwelling for leisure activities. In addition, the monthly rent per square meter of housing space, measured in Swiss francs was included as a continuous variable to control for differences in housing costs and quality. Higher rents tend to be associated with better housing infrastructure or greater housing space, factors that may enhance both the feasibility and the comfort of teleworking. The definition of the variables used in our regression models can be found in Table 1.

3.4. Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics of all regression variables are presented in Table 1. Overall, 57% of respondents are female, and the average age is 40 years. The average household comprises 2.4 persons, with a mean annual income of CHF 89,780. Comparing the sample to the Swiss working population [3,68] reveals that the sample contains a higher share of women (57% vs. CH 47%) and is somewhat younger (40 vs. CH 42 years). Household size aligns well with national figures (2.4 vs. CH 2.2 persons), while median annual household income in the sample is slightly below the national median (CHF 89,780 vs. CH CHF 95,000).

Regarding sociodemographic characteristics, teleworking households include a larger proportion of women and are more frequently found among couples without or with children, whereas non-teleworking households include more single and older households. Professional status also differs, with high-status occupations being more prevalent among teleworkers (16%) than among non-teleworkers (4%). Location-specific characteristics show that public transport use is more common among teleworkers (52%) than non-teleworkers (38%), and the majority of respondents live in urban municipalities, followed by mixed and rural areas.

Households report an average housing space of 105 m² with 3.8 rooms, corresponding to a weighted housing space per person of 64.8 m². Teleworkers show slightly higher values in housing space (65.8 m²) than non-teleworkers (63.0 m²).

Analysis by household type and housing space (see Table 2) reveals that the average housing space for a single household is 3.3 rooms and housing space of 86 m². Couple households without children have an average housing space of 107 m² and 3.7 rooms. For couple households with children, the average housing space is 113 m² and 4.1 rooms. Shared flats have an average housing space of 107 m² with an average of 3.8 rooms. The average weighted housing space per person is notably elevated across all household types. Couple households with children exhibit the lowest weighted housing space per person (54 m²), while single-person households exhibit above-average housing space (85.6

m²). In comparison to the mean housing space in Switzerland in 2024 of 102 m² [12], the mean housing space is significantly higher in the sample. This discrepancy may be attributed to the limitations of the study, as it only considers 3- to 5-room dwellings in agglomerations.

Dwelling characteristics show that 17% of teleworking households have access to an additional room outside the dwelling, and 61% use their home for hobbies or leisure activities. The average rent per square meter is slightly higher among teleworkers (CHF 19.3) than non-teleworkers (CHF 18.3). The free-room indicator suggests moderate under-occupancy in both groups.

4. Results

4.1. Likelihood for teleworking

First, we analyse the factors influencing the likelihood of telework, as represented by model 1 and Eqs. (1) and (2). The analysis is based on a probit model that explains the probability of teleworking (see Table 3). In addition to the estimated regression coefficients, the direct impact of individual factors on the probability of teleworking was quantified using average marginal effects.

The results show that women are significantly less likely to telework (coef=-0.19*). Specifically, the marginal effect is around 6.7 percentage points. There are also differences among older workers: people aged 55 to 65 are around 13 percentage points less likely to telework (-0.38**) than those under 35.

Household type is another significant predictor. Couples, both with (0.35*) and without children (0.44**), are significantly more likely to telework. This effect is particularly pronounced among couples without children (16 percentage points) and other households (23 percentage points, 0.68**). Although there is a positive trend among single parents (0.20), this is not statistically significant. Having children under the age of 14 in the household is also associated with an increased likelihood of teleworking (0.19+).

Professional status has a particularly strong influence. Those with medium or high professional status are significantly more likely to telework (0.23* respectively 0.87***). For those with a high occupational status, the effect is almost 28 percentage points.

The housing situation also plays a role. Having available space for telework, whether through additional rooms outside (0.35**) or having more free rooms (0.14*), significantly increases the likelihood of teleworking. Additionally, there is a notable impact related to public transport. Those who use public transport are more likely to telework

Table 2
Average housing space and household size by household type.

Household type	Average number of rooms	Average housing space in m ²	Average weighted housing space per person in m ²	Average household size	N
Single household	3.6	84.7	84.7	1.0	189
Couple household w/o children	3.7	103.7	66.8	2.0	307
Couple household with child (ren)	4.1	109.1	53.9	3.6	326
Single-parent family	3.7	93.8	58.5	2.4	79
Shared household	3.8	103.1	57.5	2.8	47
Overall	3.8	100.9	64.8	2.4	948

This table reports the averages of the number of rooms, the housing space and the household size by household type.

(0.33***), potentially as a means of avoiding long or stressful commutes. Finally, regional differences emerge, with people in rural areas teleworking significantly less often than those in urban areas (-0.58**). The difference is around 21 percentage points.

Overall, the results highlight that the use of teleworking is not evenly distributed across the working population, but is influenced by various sociodemographic and housing-specific factors. Occupational status, household type and housing conditions are key determinants. The findings suggest that those variables are also important for the housing space.

4.2. Influencing housing space

The model presented in Table 4 examines the factors influencing housing space. The regression analysis shows how teleworking, and which socio-economic and housing-related factors significantly influence the amount of housing space per person. The average housing space per person is around 83.8 square meters.

The linear regression model shows that several variables have a significant influence on housing space, in particular teleworking (coef=-5.97***). Teleworkers occupy on average, around 6.0 m² more housing space per person.

A higher rent per square metre has a significant negative effect on housing space, for each additional unit of rent, the housing space is reduced by approximately 1.4 m² (***). There are further significant differences in household type. A particularly clear influence can be seen in single-person households, which on average have 19.1 m² more housing space per person (***). Households with children, including couples with children (-6.53***), single parents (-5.81**) and other household types (-7.46***), consume significantly less housing space per person than childless couples. In addition, with each additional child under the age of 14, housing space per person falls by a further 4.8 m² (***). The first model indicates that individuals in family or shared households have a higher likelihood of teleworking. As these household types involve more occupants, they may housing space per person despite higher overall dwelling size.

Professional status has a significant influence on housing space per person. On average, individuals with medium professional status occupy 4.3 m² more housing space per person (***) than those with low status, while individuals with high status occupy 9.2 m² more per person (***).

The urban residential area also plays an important role. On average, people in rural areas live in 8.1 m² more space than those in cities (**). However, the difference in mixed areas is not statistically significant (1.24). This possibly reflects different housing cost structures and the availability of housing space per person in different regions.

5. Discussion of the likelihood of teleworking and housing space

The two models describe the relationship between telework and housing space. The results show a significant association between teleworking and increased housing space per person. Teleworkers use, on average, nearly six square metres more housing space per person than non-teleworkers. This is in line with other studies [35]. Teleworkers need at least a quiet or a dedicated workspace, ideally in a separate home office room [34]. The integration of paid work into domestic practices [19,45] can increase both the need for additional housing space and the requirements for space quality, such as noise control, natural light, and furnishings. Balthasar et al. [4] found that teleworkers are significantly more likely than non-teleworkers to have a separate home office room. These results may be indicative of spillover effects on housing space due to telework.

The observed association between telework and housing space should be interpreted with caution, as the relationship may be bidirectional. On the one hand, larger or more suitable homes may facilitate teleworking by providing the spatial conditions. On the other hand, teleworking itself may increase the demand for additional housing

Table 3
Probit model for explaining the likelihood of teleworking.

		coef	SE	Pr (> t)	Sig	Margin (dy/dx)	SE	Pr (> t)	Sig.
Intercept	(constant)	-0.33	0.18	0.06	+				
Gender	female (ref.: male)	-0.19	0.09	0.03	*	-0.07	0.03	0.03	*
Age	35-54 years	-0.04	0.10	0.67		-0.01	0.03	0.67	
	55-65 years (ref.: 20-29 years)	-0.38	0.13	0.01	**	-0.13	0.05	0.01	**
Household type	Couple household w/o children	0.44	0.13	0.00	**	0.16	0.04	0.00	**
	Couple household with children	0.35	0.17	0.04	*	0.13	0.13	0.04	*
	Single-parent family	0.20	0.18	0.26		0.07	0.07	0.26	
	Others (ref.: single household)	0.68	0.23	0.00	**	0.23	0.07	0.00	**
Number of children under 14 years		0.15	0.08	0.07	+	0.05	0.03	0.07	+
Professional status	Middle	0.23	0.11	0.04	*	0.08	0.04	0.04	*
	High (ref.: low)	0.87	0.19	0.00	***	0.28	0.05	0.00	***
Room outside of dwelling		0.35	0.13	0.01	**	0.12	0.04	0.01	**
Free rooms indicator		0.14	0.06	0.02	*	0.05	0.02	0.02	*
Public transport use		0.33	0.09	0.00	***	0.115	0.03	0.00	***
Degree of urbanisation	Mixed	0.06	0.10	0.58		0.02	0.03	0.58	
	Rural (ref.: urban)	-0.58	0.19	0.00	**	-0.21	0.07	0.00	**
n = 948									
Log pseudolikelihood									
Wald chi ² (15)									
Prob > chi ²									
Pseudo R ²									

Note: *** p < 0.001, ** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05, + p < 0.1, Ref. = reference category, SE. = Standard error, Sig. = Significance.

space, for example when households allocate a separate home office room. The model indicates that household with higher professional status and those with children under the age of 14 are more likely to telework. At the same time, these groups tend to live in larger homes. This suggests that the reported association may therefore reflect both selection into telework-supportive housing conditions and subsequent spatial adaptations related to telework. Given the cross-sectional design of the study, these dynamics cannot be disentangled and no causal conclusions can be drawn.

The binary operationalization of telework allows for a clear distinction between teleworkers and non-teleworkers and thus provides a basis for identifying general patterns in the relationship between telework and housing space. At the same time, the academic debate has shifted towards more differentiated perspectives on telework arrangements, considering variations in frequency, intensity and different telework locations and their distinct effects [22]. This development highlights that the relationship between telework and housing demand is not necessarily uniform, but may vary depending on how regularly telework is performed. The adaptation of housing space, including the need for a separate home office room, is likely to depend strongly on how frequently telework is practiced. Z'Rotz et al. [69] show that higher frequencies of teleworking are associated with greater amounts of workspace and ICT infrastructure. Similar to Hostettler Macias et al. [48], it could be the longer individuals engage in teleworking, the more likely they are to adjust their residential preferences. This suggests that teleworkers adapt their housing environment to suit their working situation. Future research would benefit from more differentiated measures of telework arrangements in order to better capture these differentiated relationships.

Teleworking is dependent on professional status and spatial facilities, a privilege enjoyed by high-income households, highlighting that not all employee can telework. As a result, highly skilled workers enjoy greater flexibility in their residential choice [48], and are therefore more likely to have suitable environments for teleworking [52]. This could lead to socially fragmented demand for housing: wealthy households expand their housing space for teleworking, while lower-income groups continue to live in central locations with limited housing space. This exacerbates social inequalities in the housing and labour markets.

From a sufficiency perspective, teleworking creates a double tension at the level of housing and at overall sustainability. On the one hand, telework contributes to a further increase in the already high level of housing space in Switzerland. The practical implemented of telework such as workspace design is crucial [16,70]. Achieving sufficiency in the

Table 4
OLS regression model for explaining the average weighted housing space per person.

		coef	SE	Pr (> t)	Sig.
Intercept	(constant)	83.77	3.20	0.00	***
Telework		5.97	1.06	0.00	***
Dwelling use for leisure activities		0.61	1.02	0.55	
Rent per square meter		-1.37	0.13	0.00	***
Gender	female (ref.: male)	-0.98	1.03	0.34	
Age	35-54 years	0.61	1.16	0.60	
	55-65 years (ref.: 20-29 years)	0.49	1.66	0.77	
Household type	Single household	19.05	1.62	0.00	***
	Couple household with children	-6.53	1.71	0.00	***
	Single-parent family	-5.81	2.35	0.01	**
	Others (ref.: couple household w/o children)	-7.46	2.25	0.00	***
Number of children under 14 years		-4.84	0.72	0.00	***
Professional status	Middle	4.25	1.19	0.00	***
	High (ref.: low)	9.22	1.99	0.00	***
Degree of urbanisation	Mixed	1.24	1.17	0.29	
	Rural (ref.: urban)	8.10	2.74	0.00	**
n = 948					
R ² = 45.5%					
F-statistic F(15, 935)				0.00	***

Note: *** p < 0.001, ** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05, Ref. = reference category, SE. = robust Standard error, Sig. = Significance.

housing and workspaces requires considering how telework can be organised in space-efficient housing.

On the other hand, the findings suggest that the sustainability implications of telework should be discussed from a broader perspective and include different domains [7]. If telework increases the demand for private housing space, its environmental benefits may be partly offset by higher housing space, which raises broader questions for urban planning and housing markets. From a planning perspective, this implies that telework should not be treated solely as a transport issue [2], but also as a driver of changing spatial demands within housing and neighbourhoods. From a housing perspective, increased demand for larger or more specialized home may place additional pressure on already constrained housing markets. Beyond these market effects, telework can also contribute to greater spatial dispersion and intensify processes of urban sprawl. This is particularly relevant from a sustainability perspective, as compact housing and compact cities can reduce the ecological footprint of housing [71].

In addition, from an organizational perspective, the findings indicate that the spatial requirements of telework cannot be treated as a purely private matter, since the ability to telework productively depends partly on housing resources. This suggests that the infrastructure needed for telework should not be shifted entirely to the private household as it may reinforce inequalities in access to suitable housing conditions for telework. In vein of Wagner, van der Werff and Steg [72], teleworking raises the question of how individualised housing space demand can be translated into collaborative working structures and more space-efficient housing. Shared spaces in compact housing developments can help mitigate the spatial constraints of small homes [73]. Neighbourhood-based coworking spaces, shared work facilities, and more flexible housing designs may help decouple telework from the need for additional private housing space and thereby reduce potential spillover effects in the housing.

6. Conclusion and outlook

To sum up, the research question can be answered in the following manner: the analysis confirms that teleworking has a positive association with housing space. This is due both to the actual space required for paid work in the home and to the socio-economic structures of households in which telework is more common. The likelihood of teleworking is influenced by a variety of factors. Particularly relevant are professional status, household type and parenthood (having children under 14 years of age) as well as the location of the home (urban vs. rural) and public transport use. The regression analysis on housing space per person shows that socio-economic such as household type and professional status and housing-related factors as rent per square meter have a significant association with housing space per person. Teleworkers tend to have more housing space per person, especially those in higher professional status and those living alone than non-teleworkers.

The results suggest that teleworking is associated with an increased demand for housing space. Teleworking usually requires at least one quiet workspace at home and depending on the household circumstances. Further, teleworking is regarded as a new residential function. Therefore, it expands how the home is used and increases demands for a better quality of housing, for example in the form of an additional home office room, more light or good acoustics. Thirdly, this trend is reinforced by social selectivity. People with higher education and higher professional status are more likely to telework.

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of the study. First, the sample consists exclusively of households living in 3- to 5-room dwellings outside city centre areas. As a result, housing space in this study may be slightly overestimated compared with the Swiss average, since average dwelling sizes in city centres are smaller than in agglomerations and rural regions [12].

Second, the analysis is based on a cross-section, meaning that causal statements cannot be made. Temporal dynamics, such as changes due to

the pandemic or long-term shifts in lifestyle, are also not considered.

Third, methodological limitations must also be considered. There is a risk of mutual causality and endogeneity (e.g. between professional status, residential location, housing space and teleworking) that could not be controlled. Additionally, variables that were not collected, such as working time models, telework arrangements or occupational types, could influence the target variables and distort the results.

A further point concerns the operationalization of telework as a binary variable. The implications of telework for housing space are likely to vary depending on how often telework is performed. The present analysis therefore identifies a general association between telework and housing space, while leaving variation in telework intensity unobserved. Initial studies indicate that increased teleworking is associated with more frequent adjustments in work habits (e.g. [48]). Milián Bernal et al. [51] further demonstrate that varying levels of teleworking correspond to distinct spatial strategies. Future research should employ more detailed measures of telework arrangements to clarify how different intensities of teleworking affect housing space and housing preferences.

Taken together, these limitations highlight the need for further research that can address these gaps and provide a more comprehensive understanding of teleworking arrangements and its implications. Further research involving longitudinal, and more context-sensitive analyses would be useful for capturing the interactions between paid work, telework arrangements, housing and sustainability more accurately.

However, the effects of telework are manifold. This paper provides initial evidence that teleworking in Switzerland is associated with higher housing space, suggesting that its environmental benefits may be partially offset. Teleworking arrangements are linked to rebound and spillover effects due to more non-work mobility, increased housing space and higher ICT use. Thus, the environmental benefits of teleworking depend on how it is implemented in practice and on the layout of the workspace [70,74–76]. While these ecological implications highlight the need for a comprehensive assessment of teleworking [7], it is equally important to consider its social dimensions. The study highlights the ambivalence and tensions associated with teleworking. For telework to contribute to sustainability, it must be implemented in socially and ecologically responsible ways.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jana Z'Rotz: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gabrielle Wanzenried:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Sibylla Amstutz:** Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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